

INTERFEROMETERS AND THEIR APPLICATIONS

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Annotation: This article describes the discovery of certain types of interferometers. And their workflow and applications are widely covered. At the same time, information about some interferometers is given. And the importance of interferometers in modern medicine has also been studied.

Key words: interferometers, light, differential, optics, acoustics, filters, methods.

An interferometer is a device that is used to measure the difference in the path of two waves. It consists of two mirrors that reflect light from a source onto a screen where interference occurs [7].

When light hits the interferometer, it splits into two beams that travel through different paths. On the screen of the interferometer, the interference of these two beams occurs, and the result is displayed as an interference pattern. Depending on the path difference between the two beams, the interference pattern can be either clear or blurred [1,2,7].

The principle of operation of the interferometer: It works on the basis of the phenomenon of interference, when two or more light beams are superimposed on each other, which leads to the formation of an interference pattern [7]. The principle of operation of an interferometer is based on the fact that when two or more light beams are superimposed on a screen or photographic plate, interference fringes are formed. These fringes indicate the phase difference between the two beams [3,7]. It consists of two mirrors that are perpendicular to each other. Light passes through one mirror and is reflected from the other, then passes through the first mirror again. In

this case, interference of the beam and its reflection from the mirror occurs [7]. As a result of interference, interference bands appear on the screen, which indicate the difference in phase between the beams. This phase difference can be used to measure the wavelength of light, frequency or speed of light [7]. Thus, the interferometer is an important tool for measuring various parameters of light such as wavelength, frequency, speed, etc. Its application is widespread in various fields of science and technology, including optics, radio engineering, astronomy and others [4,7].

Types of Interferometers: There are different types of interferometers that are used to measure various parameters in optics, physics and other fields of science and technology. An optical instrument used to measure the path difference between two light waves. It consists of two mirrors and two prisms that are spaced apart [5,7].

The advantages of interferometric scanners include high measurement accuracy, the ability to measure small distances and angles, and the ability to work in low-light conditions. They are widely used in various fields, including the optical industry, medicine, surveying, etc [6,7].

Laser interferometers are used to measure distances and determine deformations. They are based on the use of laser radiation to create an interference pattern. A laser interferometer is an optical device used to measure distances, angles, and other physical quantities [7,8,12]. It operates on the principle of laser beam interference, which allows an interference pattern to be created on a screen or photo sensor. Widely used in various fields, including optics, metrology, biology, medicine, materials science and others. They allow measuring distances with high accuracy and can operate in conditions of strong vibrations and turbulence [7,8].

Single-beam interferometers use a single laser beam to create an interference pattern, while dual-beam interferometers use two laser beams to create a more complex interference pattern [7,8].

Interferometers are used in various fields of science and technology, including optics, radar, acoustics, and others. Optics - widely used in optics to measure the wavelength of light, determine the shape and size of optical elements, and create optical filters [7,9]. Radar - can be used to determine the distance to an object, the

speed of an object, or to create high-precision radar systems. Acoustics - help determine the speed of sound in different environments, create acoustic filters, and measure the acoustic characteristics of objects [1,4,7,9].

Space technology - play an important role in space technology for monitoring the condition of spacecraft and satellites, determining orbits and navigation in space [7,10,11,12].

Based on the above, it can be said that interferometric methods are one of the most important tools of modern science and technology. This method has high accuracy and is considered an indispensable means of measuring various parameters of objects and environments. Today it is widely used in advanced medicine, metrology, astronomy, materials science, scientific research and other fields.

List of references:

1. Abbott V.P. et al. // Phys. Rev. Lett. 2016.
2. Малыкин Г.Б. // Опт. и спектр. 2010.
3. Малыкин Г.Б. История развития методов и интерференционных приборов для измерения малой разности оптических фаз. 2021.
4. Малыкин Г.Б. Позднякова В.И. Поляризационные эффекты в кольцевых интерферометрах. 2008.
5. Ремизов А.Н. Медицинская и биологическая физика. 2018.
6. <https://bigenc.ru/c/interferometry>. Интерферометры, 2022.
7. <https://focus-msk.ru/interferometry>...интерферометры...2024.
8. <https://library.fiveable.me/>. Interferometers and their applications. 2024.
9. <https://studfile.net/preview/Интерферометры> и их применение. Понятие об интерференционном микроскопе. 2018.
10. <https://www.ckofr.com/Интерфер.....> их назначение и принцип. 2018.
11. <https://www.opticsforhire.com/Introduction> to Interferometers... types.2024.
12. <https://www.youtube.com/Интерференция> и интерферометры. 2023.